

EVIDENCE BASED MANAGEMENT OF DADRU KUSHTA IN AYURVEDIC MEDICINE
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ABSTRACT

Introduction: skin is the largest organ of body. Nowadays incidence of fungal infection has increased. It has similar clinical features like Tinea infection. In Ayurveda it is classified under Kshudra Kushta according to Charak Acharya and under Mahakushta by Acharya Sushrut and Acharya Vagbhat.^[1] It is a superficial fungal infection presenting with circular lesions, itching, redness, and scaling. It closely resembles Tinea infections in modern dermatology.^[1] Conventional antifungal treatments often show recurrence, prompting interest in Ayurvedic alternatives. **Aim:** To study the effect of Shaman Chikitsa in Dadru Kushta. **Objectives:** 1. To overview the concept of Dadru Kushta. 2. To observe the effect if shaman Chikitsa in Dadru kushta. **Method:** A 48 years old female patient in Kaychikitsa OPD, Siddhakala Ayurved College, Sangamner having complaints of reddish discolouration patches of skin with severe itching on left leg since 2 months treated with Shaman Chikitsa. **Discussion:** Observable improvement in symptoms of Dadru Kushta. **Result:** New lesions did not appear during treatment and remarkable relief in symptoms has occurred. **Conclusion:** Shaman and Kushtaghna Chikitsa has significant relief in Dadru Kushta.

KEYWORDS: Conventional antifungal treatments often show recurrence, prompting interest in Ayurvedic alternatives.

INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ of body. Incidences of skin infections are also increasing day by day. In Ayurveda skin infections are taken under kushta. According to Acharya Charaka Dadru Kushta is classified under Kshudra Kushta and according to Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagbhata Dadru Kushta is classified under Mahakushta. Dadru is primarily caused by the vitiation of Pitta and Kapha doshas, leading to symptoms like Kandu (itching), Raga (erythema or redness), Pidaka (pustule or eruption), and Utsanna Mandala (raised circular lesions).^[2] Charaka emphasizes the doshic involvement and suggests both internal and external therapies involving Shodhana (detoxification) and Shamana (pacifying) treatments. Sushruta describes Dadru with a focus on lesion shape and chronicity, noting its resemblance to ring-like eruptions (Mandal

Kara), often spreading with intense itching.^[1] In modern medicine Dadru Kushta clinically correlates with Tinea corporis, a type of dermatophytosis, caused by fungal species like Trichophyton, Microsporum, and Epidermophyton.^[4] It presents as itchy, red, annular (ring-shaped) lesions with central clearing and raised, scaly borders. It is contagious, commonly spread via skin contact or contaminated surfaces.^[4] Management involves topical or systemic antifungal agents, but recurrence is common due to fungal persistence, resistance, or poor hygiene.

CASE REPORT

A 48 years old female patient came to OPD of Kaychikitsa department, Siddhakala Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Sangamner dist. Ahmednagar with

clinical symptoms of reddish patches on left leg with severe itching since 2 months.

History of present illness

Patient was healthy before 2 months after she developed round reddish rashes over left leg knee region with severe itching. She had taken Allopathic treatment from family doctor still symptoms didn't get relieved. Then she came to Siddhakala Ayurved Mahavidyalaya department of Kayachikitsa for treatment.

Past history

No any history of Hypertension/ Diabetes mellitus/ Any other major illness.

Surgical history

No any previous history of surgery.

On Examination

Temperature- Afebrile

Bp- 130/90 mmhg

Pulse- 78/min

RR- 20/min

Mala-samyak

Mutra -samyak

Jivha- niram

Local Examination

8 to 9 Round reddish eruptive rashes emerged with each other. No sign of discharge seen.

Observation of Lakshanas before and after the treatment

Lakshanas	Symptoms on 0 th day	Symptoms on 10 th day	After treatment On 20 th day
² Kandu (itching)	+++	--	Absent
³ Raga (Erythema or redness)	++	+	Absent
² Pidika (pustules or eruptions)	+++	++	Absent
² Mandala (raised circular lesions)	++	+	Absent

Fig – Before treatment on 0 th day.

Family History

No any family history present

Treatment given

1. Arogyavardhini vati 250 mg twice a day with Luke warm water after meal.
2. Gandhak rasayana 250 mg twice a day with lukewarm water after meal.
3. Mahamanjishthadi kwath 15 ml twice a day with half glass of water after meal.
4. Chakramarda +argvadhya lepa for local application twice a day.

Treatment was taken for 20 days.

Pathya Apathya diet

1. Avoid excess salt in diet and Excessive spices.
2. Avoid dairy products, junk food, spicy food, fermented food, oily food.
3. Avoid virudha Aahar such as milk with fruit and milk with fish.
4. Avoid sleep just after meal, late night work, overeating.
5. Eat healthy freshly cooked food, light diet.

Fig. – After treatment on 20 th day.

DISCUSSION

^[2]According to Acharya Charaka and Vagbhat Kushta are Tridoshaj.^[2] Dadru Kushta is has predominance of Pitta and Kapha Dosha.^[3] Dhatus affected mainly in Dadru Kushta are Rakta Dhatu and Ras Dhatu.^[2] In this case study, a patient diagnosed with Dadru Kushta-clinically resembling Tinea corporis-showed significant improvement following a 20 days Ayurvedic treatment regimen. The therapeutic approach included internal administration of Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha and Arogyavardhini Vati Gandhaka Rasayana, along with topical application of Chakramarda Argyvadh Lepa, known for their Kushtaghna (anti-skin disorder), Krimighna (antimicrobial), and Raktashodhaka (blood-purifying) properties. According to Ayurvedic principles, ²Dadru Kushta is caused by the vitiation of ³Pitta and Kapha doshas, affecting the skin (Twak), blood (Rakta). The formulations used in this case were selected for their ability to correct doshic imbalance. The observed reduction in itching (Kandu), erythema (Raga), and lesion size (Mandala) suggests a strong Shamana (pacifying) effect.

RESULT

The patient with remarkable clinical features of Dadru Kushta shows significant improvement in in symptoms after using Ayuvedics medicines with no any adverse reaction or complication. This outcome demonstrates a successful rate of Dadru Kushta (Tinea infection) by Ayurvedic Medicine management.

CONCLUSION

This case supports the efficacy and safety of Ayurvedic medicines in managing dermatophytic infections like Dadru Kushta, particularly in cases where conventional treatments may be insufficient or associated with recurrence.

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